

The increased use and complexity of constructing and maintaining underground spaces call for more advanced techniques for better understanding the subsurface conditions. A 3-dimensional (3-D) geologic model can be an important tool for bridging this gap, i.e. informing effective design of a tunneling project. Traditionally, only the geology along the tunnel transect is considered using cross-sections to establish baseline geologic conditions. However, the 3-D geologic model can be used to incorporate more realistic interpretations of the subsurface into the geologic baselines, and as a tool to intuitively communicate these results to designers. In recent years, novel modeling methods and the widespread availability of computer memory allows for faster, more efficient creation of 3-D geologic models.

As excavation progresses, new information on the encountered geologic units/structures can be acquired to validate and update the geologic model. Compared to traditional, explicit modeling techniques, implicit modeling allows for increased efficiency and autonomy in the geologic model creation process. This streamlined workflow opens new possibilities for utilizing the geologic model as a design tool, including the ability to incorporate newly acquired data and perturb input parameters to test geologic predictions and characterize model uncertainty.

The extreme depth and lateral extent of hard rock tunnels often results in highly uncertain geologic characterization. Prior to tunneling in hard rock, the discontinuity condition of the rockmass must be interpolated between and extrapolated from initial observations, i.e. borings and outcrops. A more robust approach than interpolating numerical values of rockmass quality (e.g. Rock Mass Rating, Q-system) involves the modeling of the discontinuity surfaces themselves.

Here we utilize implicit geologic modeling using the potential-field method to use data collected during excavation to characterize the extent of encountered discontinuities in order to better inform the extrapolation of these structures beyond the tunnel face.

Following an initial site investigation, utilize the speed of implicit geologic modeling to create multiple models respecting the hard data with uncertainty via different interpretations. Geologic knowledge will be used to enforce realistic geologic predictions during modeling, for example by extrapolating a fault from a surface trace using measured dip and dip azimuth. Predicted models will be validated against newly acquired data (e.g. excavation mapping or additional investigations) and information gained will be used to update predictions away from the encountered geology. Statistical tools such as residual error or the confusion matrix can provide a degree of validation for predicted models, while interpretive use of geologic knowledge can be used to eliminate unrealistic predictions through Bayesian inference. Incorporating the new data and updated geologic predictions, the 3-D geologic model can be iteratively updated until a full characterization of the geology encountered along the excavation is achieved. Uncertainty can be quantified at any stage of modeling using an ensemble of equiprobable models to communicate the degree of variability in the expected geology.